

Impact of Commercial Bank Development on Economic Performance in the Selected G7 and African Countries

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ABSTRACT

To examine the impact of commercial bank development on economic growth, adopting panel autoregressive distributed lag model (P-ARDL). Thus, we used bank credit to the private sector, domestic credit to the private sector, financial deepening, bank deposit and lending rate to measure the commercial bank development while we used control of corruption, regulatory quality, rule of law and government effectiveness to account for governance and regulatory quality, and we controlled for the influence of the macroeconomic variables by including current account balance, exchange rate, inflation rate and personal income in the model. To account for growth, we used gross domestic product per capita to measure the economic growth. We employed time series data spanning from the period of 1996 to 2018. The result reveals that commercial bank development has a significant positive impact on economic growth. From our findings, there is the positive long-run relationship between bank credit to the private sector and economic growth suggesting that commercial bank development leads to economic growth. This indicates that banking industry development tends to improve the productive capacity of G7 and African economies as in the case of supply leading hypothesis. However, poor government effectiveness, regulatory quality, role of law and control of corruption destroys the growth of commercial banks especially as its evidential in our findings in Africa, therefore Governments are advised to seek for policies that minimizes corruption, promotes government effectiveness and regulatory quality.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Economic growth is one of the greatest goals of the countries of the world. As a convention, the development processes needs some prerequisite requirements in order to satisfy human wants and that may occurs through financing investment and production which have its root on the commercial bank development. However, in the words of Ngugi Amanja and Maana, Gurley and Shaw and Sharma and V.N.Saxena, among others, commercial banks contributes significantly to economic growth of a nation. A well-functioning commercial sector can shoot economic growth very high (Schumpeter, 1912 and Levine, 1997) due to the fact that financial sector provides positive avenues in several ways which increases people's standards of living and reduce

the poverty level. This led to an increased desire for enquiries into the role of commercial bank in economic growth of a nations rose on the high side by researchers, academia and policy makers as it can be empirically attested to be positive in the literature such as (Yakubu and Affoi, 2014; Aurangzeb, 2012; Olokoyo, 2011; McKinnon, 1973; Shaw, 1973; and Schumpeter, 1911) among others contending that there's no doubt that commercial bank development leads to robust economic growth. As a result of this, with a reserve of 10% of deposits, every bank would lend out 90% of any deposit, which would increase deposits with other banks, resulting to multiple creation of deposits in the banking system (Friedrich von Hayek (1929)). This is achieved from the enormous and impeccable growth-inducing functions commercial banks

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and financial sectors plays in the development of economy. For instance, in Fig. 1 and 2 below, there exist positive long run economic relationship between commercial bank

development and economic growth in G-7 and African countries respectively in 2014, 2016 and 2018.

Source: Data from World Atlas 2018; computed by the Author with the aid of Excel 2013.

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Obviously, banking system is important to the economic growth due to these following reasons; first, because of its ability to gather and attract deposits from savers. Secondly, its role in providing loans to encourage investment and production. Thirdly, its ability in creating economic expansion to the most of economic sectors such as; agriculture, industry and trade sector. Fourth, due to the

intermarry role between savers and borrowers. Finally, due to its contribution to the formation of initial capital for investment projects. The causal relationship that exists between bank credits and economic growth has been widely debated and attested to be controversial in financial literatures such as (Medjahed and Gherbi (2016), Frikha and McMillan (2016), Prochniak and Wasiak (2017), Zhao (2017), Inous

and Hamon (2016) Yang (2019)) among others. For instance, Hicks (1969) stated that financial system is boosting economic growth and development and this is called “supply leading”, because financial institutions provide more fund to support economic activities which create credits and cause economic growth. Similarly, King and Levine (1993) and Miller (1998) asserted that economic growth is a result from financial development. This implies that financial development has significant positive impact on economic growth. Nevertheless, Goldsmith (1969) proved that economic development is a root or ground of financial development which implies that higher economic growth rates cause higher demand of credits.

However, on the other hand, in spite of the remarkable volumes of literature and theories on commercial bank development prompting economic growth, in terms of the number of banks in operation, bank density and their assets portfolio relative to other non-bank institutions in the financial sector, its performance has remained relatively unsatisfactory with respect to the growth process. For instance, in the case of Nigeria, as it was traced by Maduka and Onwuka (2013) who states that “Despite the growth record of banks and non-bank financial institutions in Nigeria, and financial liberalization policy, the Nigeria economic growth is sluggish. The per capita income is less than \$4,000. Most of the industries are winding up and thus giving rise to unemployment”. At this juncture, it might be quite pertinent for one to ask if the development of commercial banks are capable of promoting economic growth or not. This may be partly due to dearth of empirical studies which will shed light on how commercial banks can contribute meaningfully to economic growth in the sampled countries.

In particular, to determine the contribution of commercial bank to economic growth, the nexus between economic growth and investment, quality of service, savings mobilization, quality of payment systems and banking

security must be clearly understood through an empirical investigation. This is so far lacking or insufficiently explored in the previous studies. Therefore, this study seeks to provide the answers to the question “does commercial bank development promote economic growth or not?” With empirical studies from the selected G-7 and African countries using Panel ARDL method with critical reviews of theoretical and empirical literature, therefore we would come to the conclusion of our investigation determining whether commercial bank development stimulates economic growth or not.

2. REVIEW OF THEORETICAL AND EMPIRICAL LITERATURE

2.1 Theoretical Literature

Economic growth is one of the most important aspect of a notions in the global economy. In modern growth theory, it was stated that “human desires and unlimited wants leads to ever-increasing productivity and economic growth. It further argues that real gross domestic product (GDP) per capita will perpetually increase because of people are in pursuit of profits. As pronounced by Theil (2001), out of the whole theories in the modern growth theory, A K growth model which demonstrates the three important connections between financial variables and economic activity ($Y_t = AK_t$; where Y_t is output in period t produced by capital K, and A symbolizes capital productivity) is suitable. This model assumes that an efficient financial system reduces the loss of resources required to allocate capital and can be used to derive the optimal size of the financial system (Theil, 2001). The more efficient the transformation of savings into investment, the lower the loss of resources and the more the savings can be used for productive investments thus leading to a positive feedback. This positive feedback effect between finance and growth is demonstrated in Harrison et al (1999) study as in below.

Figure 3: The Channels of Commercial Bank Development Influencing Economic Growth

Source: (Robinson, 1952); (Levine, 1997) and (Theil, 2001)

The positive feedback effects through the credit and investment channels on the finance-economic growth relationship is evidently productive in mobilizing savings for investment, facilitating and encouraging inflows of foreign capital (including foreign direct investment, portfolio investment, bonds and remittances), optimizing the allocation of capital between competing uses, and ensuring that capital goes to the most productive end use (FitzGerald, 2006). In this regard, Levine (1997) identified five basic roles of commercial banks plays in economic growth (1) saving mobilization (2) risk management (3) acquiring information about investment opportunities (4) monitoring borrowers and exerting corporate control (5) facilitating the exchange of goods and services. These leads to positive feedbacks effects from commercial banks to economic growth. (Figure 3).

Deployment of savings is an important function of the commercial bank towards development of economic growth. The provision of saving facilities or transaction with bank accounts enables households to store their money in a secure place and allows money to be kept for productive use in the economy. Bringing savings into the financial sector where they can be utilized productively could itself make a significant contribution to economic growth in the country, in particular, because it contributes to increased productivity and capital accumulation channels. At the same time, credit may also be made available to finance investment such as in education, agriculture, science and technology, infrastructural development, which promotes accumulation of human capital (De-Gregorio, 1996). Financial institutions may also increase the rate of technological progress by identifying and thus allocating capital towards those innovations with the best chances of succeeding (King and Levine, 1993b).

A well-developed financial system no doubt redeems a nation from economic quagmire and plug it to static economic growth, this is evidential in Fractional Reserve Theory as propounded by Gurley and Shaw (1955) which states that “banks accepts deposits from customers and make loans available to borrowers, while holding in reserve an amount equal to only a fraction of the bank's deposit liabilities”. This theory of banking argues that each bank is a financial intermediary. However, it disagrees with the former reserve theories concerning the collective, macroeconomic role of banks: it argues that, together, the banking system creates money, through the process of ‘multiple deposit expansions’. Thus when Gurley and Shaw (1955) argued that bank and non-bank financial institutions are largely similar in that they are both financial intermediaries able to ‘create financial claims’. Gurley and Shaw was challenged in favour and against their theory during the 1950s and 1960s in influential journals by, among others, Culbertson (1958), Aschheim (1959), Warren Smith (1959), Solomon (1959), Paul Smith (1966) and Guttentag and Lindsay (1968), many of whom were supporters of the fractional reserve theory. Phillips’

citation of the credit or money multiplier rendered him one of the earlier and most influential economists to formulate the mechanics of fractional reserve banking. According to Phillips: “what is true for the banking system as an aggregate is not true for an individual bank that constitutes only one of many units in that aggregate.” Crick (1927) is another supporter of this theory. He argues that while each bank is a financial intermediary, the banking system as a whole can creates money. Like later Keynes and Tobin, Crick adopted the habit of placing the concept of creation in inverted commas (credit “creation”). This implies skepticism, if not even derision and ridicule for those who believe in the ability of banks to create credit. Why not entirely deny the potential for banks to create credit and money, Crick (1927) and colleagues succeeded in downplaying the significance of any such action and re-assuring the public – or academia – that all was under control, as the money creation was the result of a kind of diffuse process, a technical detail that experts might debate, but which was of little direct consequence for the economic model builder.

Friedrich von Hayek's first book revealed him to be also a supporter of the fractional reserve theory of banking (Hayek, 1929): He argues that “with a reserve of 10%, every bank would lend out 90% of any deposit, which would increase deposits with other banks, resulting in a multiple creation of deposits in the banking system”. Meanwhile, Keynes (1930) supports the fractional reserve theory, citing both Phillips (1920) and Crick (1927) approvingly. But he then discusses the concept of money ‘creation’ by referring to any increase in bank deposits as the ‘creation’ of deposits: “There can be no doubt that, in the most convenient use of language, all deposits are ‘created’ by the bank holding them”. It is certainly not the case that the banks are limited to that kind of deposit, for the creation of which it is necessary that depositors should come on their own initiative bringing cash or cheques”. Keynes may have been referring to bank transfers as the kind of deposit that allows a bank to ‘create’ a deposit, while remaining a mere financial intermediary, since Keynes (1930) deploys the expression ‘creation of deposits’ also for the instance of a cash deposit at a bank, arguing that: “only the bank itself can authorize the creation of a deposit in its books entitling the customer to draw cash or to transfer his claim to the order of someone else”.

So ‘deposit creation’ “in the most convenient use of language” here is simply the act of recording a deposit in the bank's account, i.e. a bank accounting entry. If the adjustment of an account is termed the ‘creation’ of such an accounting record, by this definition banks are of course ‘creating’ entries whenever a transaction is made. However, by this definition any non-bank corporation would equally be ‘creating’ assets and liabilities on its balance sheet, whenever a transaction is entered into the firm's accounts. Thus Keynes' terminology does not serve to clarify. The widely read contemporary study by Stiglitz (1997) also favours

the fractional reserve theory, and mirrors Keynes' ambiguous terminology: “The process of multiple-deposit creation may seem somewhat like “a magician pulling rabbits out of a hat:” it seems to make something out of nothing. But it is, in fact a real physical process. Deposits are created by making entries in records; today electronic impulses create records on computer tapes. The rules of deposit creation are rules specifying when you may make certain entries in the books. It is these rules – in particular, the fractional reserve requirements – that give rise to the system's ability to expand deposits by a multiple of the original deposit increase”. Again, the ‘creation’ of deposits and loans is defined by the creation of an accounting record. Such terminology distracts from the question whether individual banks can uniquely create new purchasing power out of nothing, and hence cause an increase in total balances without a commensurate decrease. But at least Stiglitz's adherence to the fractional reserve theory of banking is clear-cut. What must be the most influential post-war textbook in economics by Samuelson (1948) squarely addresses the question at hand: The original first edition deals with the third theory of banking, the credit creation theory and dismisses it. Under the heading “Can banks really create money?”, Samuelson argues against “false explanations still in wide circulation”: “According to these false explanations, the managers of an ordinary bank are able, by some use of their fountain pens, to lend several dollars for each dollar left on deposit with them. No wonder practical bankers see red when such behavior is attributed to them. They only wish they could do so. As every banker well knows, he cannot invest money that he does not have; and any money that he does invest in buying a security or making a loan will soon leave his bank”.

The financial sector provides services which have been identified as germane for the growth of an economy. The principal function of the financial sector is the movement of financial resources between different units in an economy through the process of financial intermediation. Thus, resulting to supply-leading hypothesis which assumes that financial development is the driver of economic growth. According to Schumpeter (1911), a well-functioning financial sector is necessary to facilitate growth in the real sector which resultantly leads to economic growth. In other words, economic growth is reliant on how well the financial sector is deepened or developed. As the financial sector deepens, there is increase in the supply of financial services. The hypothesis is alternatively referred to as “finance-led growth hypothesis”.

The central argument underlying supply-leading hypothesis is that financial deepening is a determinant factor for economic growth. It posits that optimal allocation of resources is an outcome of financial sector development (Hurlin and Venet, 2008). The supply-leading hypothesis suggests that causality flows from finance to economic growth with no feedback response from economic growth. A

well-developed financial sector is a pre-condition for economic growth. McKinnon (1973) and Shaw (1973) argue that a well-developed financial sector minimizes transaction and monitoring costs and asymmetric information; thus there is improvement in financial intermediation. The existence of well-developed financial sector enhances the creation of financial services as well as accessibility to them in anticipation to their demand by participants in the real sector of the economy. The supply-leading hypothesis presumes that the economy responds to growth in the real sector facilitated by financial development.

Contradictory to supply-leading hypothesis was pioneered by Robinson (1952) who stated that “financial deepening is dependent on growth that occurs in the economy”. This stance is embedded in the demand-following or growth-led finance hypothesis. It suggests that causality is from economic growth to financial development. Increasing demand for financial services deepens the financial sector as the economy progresses (Calderón and Liu, 2002). Singh (1999) opines that when an economy expands, there is a rise in macroeconomic activities which resultantly develops the financial sector. Another dimension to the link between financial deepening and economic growth was propounded by Patrick (1966). This is referred to as “stage of development” hypothesis which incorporates the supply-leading and demand-following hypotheses. It posits that the causal link between financial development and economic growth alternates as the economy develops. According to Patrick (1966), “the supply-leading hypothesis holds in an economy in the early developmental stage, and as the economy grows, it fades away and the demand-following hypothesis prevails”.

The conflicting evidence on the casual link between financial development and economic growth creates the need for further research. And this is the source of our impetus to focus our research on the selected G7 and African countries. For a developing country, the existence of supply-leading hypothesis is a desideratum compared to demand-following hypothesis. This is because financial intermediaries are required to always act as growth catalysts in economic development. In G7 and African countries however, following the apriori economic expectations, it would be assumed that economic growth is dependent on the development in the financial sector. Hence, there is also the possibility of development of the financial sector to occur only when economic growth is achieved (i.e. demand-following phenomenon). Therefore, this study seeks to validate whether the supply-leading hypothesis or demand-following hypothesis holds in G7 and African countries.

2.2 Empirical Literature

In the bid to investigate the role of commercial bank development on economic growth relationship, a teaming number of scholars and academia have contributed immensely on this course with mixture of literature of both

negative and positive conclusions. For instance, Medjahed and Gherbi (2016) inspected the impact of banking sector development on growth using 11 MENA countries from period 1980 to 2012. They exposed that financial development has negative impact on economic growth both in the short run and long run in MENA countries. In the same vein, Škare and Hasić (2016) opined that almost, regardless of how financial development is measured, there is a positive relation between financial sector development and GDP per capita growth. This is also attested to the work of Caporalea et al. (2016) which suggests that Banking activity is confirmed to be a significant factor in driving local economic growth.

On the contrary, Frikha and McMillan (2016) researched the role of Islamic banks in the growth of domestic gross product in 10 developing countries (Bahrain, Egypt, Jordan, Kuwait, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, Qatar, Sudan, Turkey and United Arab Emirates). Their study used ordinary least square regression for testing 120 banks from different developing countries. They found that conventional banks support economic growth. Seven and Yetkiner (2016) provided evidence in their study on the role of financial sector development in accounting for economic growth in low, middle, and high-income countries. Using panel data from 1991 to 2011, the authors have conducted panel regression to examine whether the relationship between banks, stock markets, and economic growth differs across income levels. The empirical evidence has suggested, that in high-income countries banking development has a negative effect on economic growth. According to the researchers, this is somewhat surprising, given that the banking sector has grown remarkably over the last two decades. The authors have concluded, that a well-functioning financial system may not always be sufficient to achieve economic growth in high-income countries, while it promotes economic growth in developing countries.

A developed financial sector increases access to financial services and offers a full range of financial products and services to different economic sectors (Chavula et al., 2017). Chowdhury (2016) in studying the effect of financial development on the nexus between banks and economic growth using a dynamic panel estimation for 33 bank-receiving developing countries between 1979 and 2011. Also using four proxies/indicators of financial development: the ratio of domestic credit to private sector GDP, the ratio of total domestic credit provided by the banking sector to GDP, the degree of monetization in the economy and the M2 to GDP ratio. It shows that banks had a significant influence on the economic growth of the studied countries. In the words of KENZA, M., & EDDINE, G. N. S. (2016) while studying the effect of the development of financial sector on growth for the case of the MENA economies. They designed their research to observe the impact of financial development on economic growth in the context of the MENA region. And

they concluded by pointing out directions to improve financial development in the MENA economies by applying more financial reforms to endorse competition in the financial sector and financial structure expansion that mirrors in the progress of the quality and quantity of financial services.

Soedarmono et al. (2017) find that higher financial development measured by financial deepening and financial intermediation exhibits an inverted U-shaped relationship with economic growth, suggesting a non-linear effect. Sehrawat and Giri (2016) and Chow et al. (2018) found that bank credits have negative impact on economic growth. Khatun (2016) revealed that there is a long-run relationship between financial services and economic growth. The study also confirmed both short-run and long-run unidirectional causality running from trade in financial services to economic growth. Rani and Kumar (2018) analyzed the relationship between financial development, trade openness and economic growth. The study used Pedroni panel cointegration test to examine the existence of long-run relationship along with the panel granger causality test. The study accounted a long-run relationship among the variables. They also found that financial development to have positive effect on economic growth. Ubesie et al. (2017) wrote that deposit money banks or commonly known as commercial banks are one of the main drivers of economic development in Nigeria. It is generally accepted that intensification of financial instruments and institutions would tremendously reduce transaction and information costs in an economy which in turn influences savings rate, investment decision and technological innovative ventures (Nwakoby & Ananwude, 2016). Evans and Adeoye (2016) document the determinants of financial inclusion in Africa for the period 2005-2014, using the dynamic panel data approach. The study shows that GDP per capita, broad money (% of GDP), internet access, literacy, and Islamic banking presence are significant factors explaining the level of financial inclusion in Africa. Deposit interest rates, domestic credit provided by financial sector (% of GDP), inflation and population however have insignificant impacts on financial development.

Sharma (2016) using the Vector auto regression (VAR) and the Granger causality, have shown that various dimensions of Financial Inclusion (banking penetration, availability, and usage of banking services) have positively impacted the economic growth. Author found a bi-directional causality between the geographical penetration of banking services and the economic development and a unidirectional causality between the number of deposits and the GDP. Pradhan et al. (2016) inspected the rapport of financial inclusion with economic growth. They observed positive impacts of insurance market penetration and banks on economic growth of the sample countries Mwang'onda et al. (2018) has examined the impact of financial sector development on Economic growth; Evidence from Tanzania, by employing

Autoregressive Distributed Lags (ARDL) approach. The results show that, in both long-run and short-run, financial development exerts significant but negative effect on economic growth contrary to our expectations. Demetriades and Rousseau (2016) on the non-monotonic relationship between financial development and economic growth concluded that financial depth is no longer a significant determinant of long-run growth. They further argued that finance growth-nexus is influenced by bank regulation and supervision. Bist (2018) analyzed the long-run relationship between financial development and economic growth in 16 low-income countries, combining the cross-sectional and time series data for the period of 1995–2014. The study revealed that there exists a long-run cointegrating relationship between financial development and economic growth in low-income countries. Lipovina-Bozovic and Smolovic (2016) asserts that economic development is positively influenced by general financial development and the efficiency of the banking sector. Karagiannis and Kvedaras (2016) show that financial structure plays a central role in the relationship between financial development and economic growth.

Daouda Coulibaly (2018) in his study on the Impact of Financial Development on Economic Growth: as Countries develop financially and economically in West African Economic and Monetary Union (WAEMU) evidence shows that there is a strong impact of financial development in the case of convergence of financial systems relative to the convergence of incomes. Ibrahim and Alagidede (2017c) study in SSA however show that, while financial development positively and significantly influences economic growth, below a certain estimated threshold, finance is largely insensitive to growth while significantly influencing economic activity for countries above the thresholds. Muazu Ibrahim and Paul Alagidede (2018) studied the effects of financial development on economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa and found that that financial development positively affects growth albeit non-monotonically with variation points ranging between 27 to 29%. Following the study of Imoagwu, Chika Priscilla and Ezeanyej C.I. (2019) on financial development and economic growth nexus in Nigeria, they discovered that financial development has significant positive impact on economic growth in Nigeria in the short-run and while negative significant impact in the long-run. James Atta Peprah et al. (2019) in their study on financial development, remittances and economic growth experience from Ghana; thus, using a threshold analysis conclude that from the threshold effect, development of Ghana's financial sector over 70 percent will drag growth down. Financial development aims at ensuring that people gets access to financial services under the canopy of formal financial system so that these people may play their role in economic activity (Sethi & Acharya, 2018). In the words of Kim, Yu, and Hassan (2018) who carried out their study titled the

impact of financial development in Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) countries, however, finds a positive influence of financial development on economic growth. Also, in study by Pradhan, Arvin, et al. (2016) financial sector development for ASEAN (Association of Southeast Asian Nations) has positive relationship with economic growth.

In order to investigate the influence of financial inclusion, Mandel and Seydl (2016) conducted a research on U.S. banks' data. They found a significant contribution of financial inclusion to financial stability which in order promotes economic stability of the country. Using insurance market penetration data of ASEAN countries for the period of 1988 to 2012, Pradhan et al. (2016) inspected the rapport of financial inclusion with economic growth. They observed positive impacts of insurance market penetration on economic growth of the sample countries. Employing data for the period of 2004 to 2016, Bigirimana and Hongyi (2018) found that financial inclusion through commercial banks has major long-run effects on Rwanda's economic growth. Kim et al. (2018) employed the data of 55 OIC countries from 1990 to 2013 and found significant contributory effects of financial inclusion on economic growth. Madsen and Ang (2016) using 2SLS models using agriculture sector share of total income and unionization as instruments for financial sector development. Data averaged over 5-year intervals. They discovered that financial sector operates through four channels: knowledge production, savings, investment and schooling and they concluded that knowledge is the main financial sector development is the channel of growth.

In conclusion, from the erstwhile, Economists have been asking the question about “what’ is so special about banks” for ages when it comes to economic development? In his famous article, Corrigan (1982) provided an answer to the question which reads as follows that “banks are special because of the following reasons: (1) they provide transaction services and administer the nation's payments system; (2) provides backup liquidity to the economy; and (3) they are transmitters of monetary policy”. Due to their special function in the economy, the policymakers uses the banking system to ascertain the level of economic growth and development in an economy. Ultimately, closer investigations have shown that a well-developed commercial bank undoubtedly promotes economic growth in several ways. This fact revealed it's self in the work of Schumpeter, McKinnon (1973) and Shaw (1973) who propounded the ‘financial liberalization’ theory in 1973 by suggesting that “a higher level of banking sector development, which could be the result of financial liberalization, would lead to increased economic growth”. They argued that the financial sector could raise the volume of savings as well as the quantity and quality of investment of a nation.

Oluitan (2012) assessed the significance of real bank credit in stimulating real output growth in the case of

Nigeria. The study observes that credit Granger causes output. In testing the factors that mobilize credit, it finds that exports in general are negatively related to credit. However, while oil exports are negatively related to credit, non-oil export has positive relationship with credit. Credit is also positively linked to capital inflows and imports. Nwakanma, Nnamdi and Omojefe (2014) evaluated the nature of long-run relationship existing between bank credits to the private sector of Nigeria's economy and the nation's economic growth as well as the directions of prevailing causality between them from period 1981 and 2011. Applying Autoregressive Distributed Lag Bound (ARDL) and Granger Causality techniques, the results indicate significant long-run relationship between the study variables but without significant causality in any direction. Oluitan (2012) assessed the significance of real bank credit in stimulating real output growth in the case of Nigeria. The study observes that credit Granger causes output. In testing the factors that mobilize credit, it finds that exports in general are negatively related to credit. However, while oil exports are negatively related to credit, non-oil export has positive relationship with credit. Credit is also positively linked to capital inflows and imports.

Recently, Dembele and Machrafi (2021) studied the effect of the banking sector on economic growth in Côte d'Ivoire during 1990-2019, using a VAR model. The results indicate a positive relationship between the banking sector and economic growth in Côte d'Ivoire. Vasconcelos et al. (2021) tested the hypothesis that bank credit is necessary for economic growth, depending on the country's level of economic and financial development. To do this, the Granger causality methodology is used for panel data, with data from 106 countries for the period between 1970 and 2016. The main empirical results indicate that, in general, credit causes economic growth and vice versa. Chuba and Hitlar (2022) examined the effect of commercial bank credit allocated to the agricultural sector on economic growth in Nigeria. Their survey results revealed that commercial bank credit allocated to the agricultural sector has a significant positive effect on economic growth in Nigeria. Furthermore, Ekamena Ntsama et al. (2022) worked on the effect of bank credit and savings on growth in Cameroon using the ordinary least squares (OLS) method from 1980 to 2019. They observed that bank credit to private companies and savings had a positive and significant impact on Cameroon's economic growth during the study period.

Moreover, Ishioro (2017) analyzed the effects of banking sector reforms on economic growth in Nigeria using time series data from 1970 to 2013 and an ARDL approach. The study reveals that credit from the banking sector to the private sector has been negative and statistically insignificant in Nigeria's economic growth. Tchouassi and Tomo (2022) study the effects on economic growth of institutional reforms of financial development in the Economic and Monetary

Community of Central Africa. The results obtained using the method of generalised moments on a balanced panel show that credit to the private sector does not contribute to economic growth. Okonkwo et al. (2022) examine the contributions of the banking sector to the growth of the Nigerian economy from 1986 to 2020 using ordinary least squares regression and the Granger causality test. The results of the study revealed that bank credit has a significant negative effect on economic growth. Koutima-Banzouzi et al. (2024) examined the impact of bank credit on economic growth in six CEMAC countries from 2005 to 2021 using dynamic panel GMM analysis. The study found that bank credit has a negative and significant effect on economic growth. The authors recommend banking sector reforms and economic diversification to enhance credit effectiveness and growth outcomes. Relatedly, Ede et al. (2024) investigated the impact of forensic auditing on bank performance in Nigeria from 2013 to 2023 using ARDL and FMOLS methods. The study found that forensic auditing significantly enhances financial reporting accuracy, fraud detection, and risk management. It recommends strengthening AML frameworks through forensic auditing to boost transparency, efficiency, and stakeholder confidence in the banking sector. Furthermore, Manasseh et al. (2023) analyzed the impact of digital finance and financial inclusion on economic growth in 19 COMESA countries using panel ARDL from 1997–2018. The study found that tools like mobile banking, ATMs, POS, and financial literacy significantly promote growth. It concludes that strengthening digital finance infrastructure and inclusion policies—while addressing legal and macroeconomic challenges—can accelerate regional development. Recently, Manasseh et al. (2025) examined the impact of financial technology and innovation on bank performance in ECOWAS from 1997 to 2022 using the ARDL technique. The study found a long-run positive relationship between fintech tools—such as mobile banking, POS, and internet banking—and bank performance indicators like ROA and ROE. The authors advocate for policy and regulatory frameworks to support fintech-driven growth in the banking sector. Manasseh et al. (2024) investigated the impact of technological innovation on bank performance in 40 emerging markets from 2000 to 2021. The study found strong positive correlations and long-run relationships between innovation and bank performance using ARDL and GMM techniques. It recommends enhancing technological infrastructure and expanding digital banking to underbanked regions to boost banking sector efficiency.

3. DATA, SOURCES AND METHODS

3.1 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical underpinning of this study is based on supply-leading hypothesis. Thus, economic theory suggests that the financial sector of any economy is an engine of growth and development (Schumpeter, McKinnon (1973) and Shaw

(1973)). The argument is that if the financial sector extends credit to the productive sectors of the economy at affordable costs, the overall economy grows inclusively. This is footed in supply leading hypothesis which suggests that “financial deepening is a determining cause of economic growth”.

This hypothesis suggests that causality flows from the finance sector to economic growth with no feedback response from economic growth. The need to reduce those costs for exchanges to take place has led to the emergence of financial institutions and markets constituting the financial sector. A well-developed financial sector provides critical services to reduce those costs and thus to increase the efficiency of intermediation. It mobilizes savings, identifies and funds good business projects, monitors the performance of managers, facilitates trading and the diversification of risks, and fosters exchange of goods and services. These services result in a more efficient allocation of resources, a more rapid accumulation of physical and human capital, and faster technological innovation, thus inducing faster long-term economic growth (Chuah & Thai, 2004).

3.2 Data and Data Source

In this study, we focused on G–7 and African nations using time series data for the period of 1996 – 2018 which was also determined based on the handiness of data for the selected countries and variables in the model. To measure commercial bank development, the following variables such as the ratio of M2 (broad money) to GDP – financial deepening, bank credit to the private sector (BCPS), domestic credit to the private sector (DCPS), bank lending rate (LDR) and bank deposit (BD). The Gross domestic product per capita (GDPPC) is used as an indicator of economic growth and the current account balance, macroeconomic volatility, personal income, inflation rate and exchange rate are the control variable. Due to direct effects of governance and its regulatory quality on commercial banks, we included the following governance indicators (regulatory quality, control of corruption, government effectiveness and rule of law) to measure the impact of regulatory quality on the financial sector. We further defined our variables as in below:

Table 1: Variable Definitions

Variables	Definition	Source
GDPpc	Gross domestic product per capita	World Bank’s World Development Indicators (WDI)
CAB	Current account balance	World Bank’s World Development Indicators (WDI)
BCPS	Bank credit to the private sector	World Bank’s World Development Indicators (WDI)
DCPS	Domestic credit to the private sector	World Bank’s World Development Indicators (WDI)
LDR	Lending rate	World Bank’s World Development Indicators (WDI)
BD	Bank deposit	World Bank’s World Development Indicators (WDI)
MEV	Macroeconomic Volatility	World Bank’s World Development Indicators (WDI)
FD	Financial deepening	World Bank’s World Development Indicators (WDI)
INF	Inflation rate	World Bank’s World Development Indicators (WDI)
EXR	Exchange rate	World Bank’s World Development Indicators (WDI)
REQ	Regulatory quality	World Bank’s World Governance Indicators (WDI)
ROL	Rule of law	World Bank’s World Governance Indicators (WDI)
GEF	Government effectiveness	World Bank’s World Governance Indicators (WDI)
CC	Control of corruption	World Bank’s World Governance Indicators (WDI)
PI	Personal income	World Bank’s World Development Indicators (WDI)

Source: Author’s Concept

3.3 Model Specification

This study links economic growth, commercial bank development and institutional quality while controlling for the influence of macroeconomic volatility, financial deepening, current account balance, inflation rate, exchange rate, and personal income. This relationship is given in the log-linear empirical model below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \ln GDP_{pc,t} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln BCPS_{i,t} + \beta_2 \ln DCPS_{i,t} \\
 & + \beta_3 \ln LDR_{i,t} + \beta_4 \ln BD_{i,t} + \beta_5 \ln INSQ_{i,t} \\
 & + \beta_6 \ln MEV_{i,t} + \beta_7 \ln CAB_{i,t} + \beta_8 \ln FD_{i,t} \\
 & + \beta_9 \ln INF_{i,t} + \beta_{10} \ln EXR_{i,t} + \beta_{11} \ln PI_{i,t} \\
 & + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Where ln denotes the natural logarithm function; ε_t is the error term; GDPPC represents GDP per capita for economic growth; BCPS represents bank credit to private sector; DCPS is for domestic credit to private sector; LDR is the lending rate; BD is the bank deposit; INSQ represents institutional quality indicators (lnREQ (regulatory quality), lnGEF (government effectiveness), lnROL (rule of law), and lnCC (control of corruption)); MEV is the macroeconomic volatility; CAB is for current account balance; FD is for financial deepening represented by the ratio of M2/GDP, INF is for the inflation rate, EXR represents the exchange rate and PI is for personal income.

Following Eugene Iheanacho (2016) and Nwakanma, Nnamdi and Omojefe (2014), we utilize the Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL) approach to cointegration as propounded by (Pesaran and Pesaran, 1997) and (Pesaran and Shin, 1998) and Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001). The model was used because of some desirable statistical advantages over other co-integration techniques which include: its applicability irrespective of whether the individual regressors are integrated of the order I(0) or I(1), regardless of level of stationarity; the fact that ARDL model takes sufficient number of lags to capture the data generating process from a general to specific modelling framework (Laurenceson and Chai, 2003); also ARDL approach yields

superior estimates of long-run coefficient, and the diagnostic tests of the estimated equation are more reliable (Gerrard and Godfrey, 1998, p 235) and (Laurenceson and Chai 1998, p 405); from the ARDL model, one can derive a dynamic error correction model (ECM) through a simple linear transformation process (Banarjee and Newman, A. F. (1993), pp 50-52). The ECM also helps us to measure the short-run relationship among the model’s variables and lastly, the ARDL model is a more appropriate measure in the case of both small and large samples. For the variables incorporated in this study, we specified the ARDL model, which is outlined below:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln GDPpc_t = & \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \ln GDPpc_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{1i\Delta} \ln BCPS_{1t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{2i\Delta} \ln DCPS_{2t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{3i\Delta} \ln LDR_{3t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{4i\Delta} \ln BD_{4t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{5i\Delta} \ln INSQ_{5t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{6i\Delta} \ln MEV_{6t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{7i\Delta} \ln CAB_{7t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{8i\Delta} \ln FD_{8t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{9i\Delta} \ln INF_{9t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{10i\Delta} \ln EXR_{9t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{11i\Delta} \ln PI_{9t-i} + \Psi_1 \ln GDPpc_{t-1} + \Psi_2 \ln BCPS_{t-1} + \Psi_3 \ln DCPS_{t-1} + \Psi_4 \ln LDR_{t-1} \\ & + \Psi_5 \ln BD_{t-1} + \Psi_6 \ln INSQ_{t-1} + \Psi_7 \ln MEV_{t-1} + \Psi_8 \ln CAB_{t-1} + \Psi_9 \ln FD_{t-1} + \Psi_{10} \ln INF_{t-1} + \Psi_{11} \ln EXR_{t-1} \\ & + \Psi_{12} \ln PI_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

Where Δ = 1st difference of the variables, \ln indicates that the data set are expressed in natural logarithms, β_0 is a constant, β_1 β_{11} represent the short-run coefficients (error correction dynamic), Ψ_1 Ψ_{12} are the long-run relationship, i represents the time trend, and, ε_{it} is the white noise error.

The implementation of the ARDL approach involves two stages. First, the existence of the long-run nexus (cointegration) between variables under investigation is tested by computing the F-statistics for analyzing the significance of the lagged levels of the variables. (Pesaran, Shin, and Smith, 1999) and (Narayan, 2004) have provided two sets of appropriate critical values for different numbers of regressors (variables). This model contains an intercept, trend or both. One set assumes that all the variables in the ARDL model are of I(0), and another assumes that all the variables are I(1).

If the F-statistic lies above the upper-bound critical value for a given significance level, the conclusion is that there is a non-spurious long-run level relationship with the dependent variable. If the F-statistic lies below the lower bound critical value, the conclusion is that there is no long-run level relationship with the dependent variable. If it lies between the lower and the upper limits, the result is inconclusive. The general form of the null and alternative hypotheses for the F-statistic test is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} H_0: & \Psi_1 = \Psi_2 = \Psi_3 = \Psi_4 = \Psi_5 = \Psi_6 = \Psi_7 = \Psi_8 = \Psi_9 = \Psi_{10} = \Psi_{11} = \Psi_{12} = 0 \\ H_0: & \Psi_1 \neq \Psi_2 \neq \Psi_3 \neq \Psi_4 \neq \Psi_5 \neq \Psi_6 \neq \Psi_7 \neq \Psi_8 \neq \Psi_9 \neq \Psi_{10} \neq \Psi_{11} \neq \Psi_{12} \neq 0 \dots\dots\dots (3) \end{aligned}$$

Secondly, if the cointegration between variables is identified, then one can undertake further analysis of long-run and short-run (error correction) relationship between the variables. The error correction representation of the series can be specified as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln GDPpc_t = & \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \ln GDPpc_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{1i\Delta} \ln BCPS_{1t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{2i\Delta} \ln DCPS_{2t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{3i\Delta} \ln LDR_{3t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{4i\Delta} \ln BD_{4t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{5i\Delta} \ln INSQ_{5t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{6i\Delta} \ln MEV_{6t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{7i\Delta} \ln CAB_{7t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{8i\Delta} \ln FD_{8t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{9i\Delta} \ln INF_{9t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{10i\Delta} \ln EXR_{9t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{11i\Delta} \ln PI_{9t-i} + \phi ECT_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

Where \emptyset is the speed of adjustment parameter and ECT is the residuals obtained from equation 1 (i.e. the error correction term). The coefficient of the lagged error correction term (ζ) is expected to be negative and statistically significant to further confirm the existence of a cointegrating relationship. A negative and significant ECM_{t-1} coefficient (ζ) implies that any short term disequilibrium between the dependent and explanatory variables will converge back to the long-run equilibrium relationship. This study implements the ARDL bounds cointegration analysis using Eviews 10.

4. EMPIRICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

From the literature, it has been highly opined by the researchers that commercial banks have impeccable growth function it plays on economic growth (see: Friedrich von Hayek (1929) among others. Indeed, the expansion of Pan-African banks has promoted greater economic integration and has increasingly filled the gap left by European and U.S. banks, but it also poses challenges. These include derisory supervisory oversight on a consolidated basis and relatively weak internal governance frameworks. Financial institutions serve as the intermediary that allocates resources from savers to investors across economic sectors. Due to the close linkage with domestic and external economic sectors, the primary role of central bank of a country would be to supervise financial institutions with the objectives to ensure the followings: (1) financial institutions are prudent and have proper risk management system (2) to enhance overall efficiency of financial institutions (3) to ensure good corporate governance of financial institutions (4) to ensure fairness of financial institutions in doing business with their customers, and (5) to supervise financial institutions in order to safeguard economic and financial stabilities. As mentioned in the introductory section, the objective of this paper is to analyze the impact of commercial bank development on economic growth in selected G7 and African countries therefore, we adopted panel autoregressive distributed lag model (P-ARDLM) Bound testing cointegration approach which allow variables to be integrated of either order zero I(0) of order one I(1) or both. We start our estimation by testing the nature of the variables used in the study as in below.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 describes the descriptive statistics of each variable. The average value of the gross domestic product per capita is 1.090, with a standard deviation of 1.420. The mean value of BCPS is 2.935 with a standard deviation of 2.261. The mean value of domestic credit to the private sector (DCPS) is 0.605, while the standard deviation is 1.35. The mean value of current account balance is 0.902 while the standard deviation is 1.462. The average value of lending rate is 0.999 while the standard deviation is 1.564281. Bank deposit (BD) has an average of 1.125 with standard deviation 3.853. The MEV has a mean value 1.938 with standard deviation 2.857. Financial deepening has an average of 1.857 with a standard deviation 2.802. The inflation rate has a mean value 2.283 with a standard deviation 3.065. Exchange rates mean is 2.104 with a standard deviation 2.743. The average of REQ is -0.111 with a standard deviation 1.439. The mean value of ROL is -0.545 while its standard deviation is 0.982. The GEF has a mean value -0.507 and standard deviation 0.910. The average of control of corruption (CC) is -0.429 with a standard deviation of 0.901 and the personal income (PI) has a mean value of 2.542 and standard deviation 4.382. The values of gross domestic product per capita, bank credit to the private sector and domestic credit to the private sector show that commercial banks contributes more to the overall economic growth G7 and African countries. The Jarque-Bera for all the variables a statistically significant at 1% significant level implying that all the variables a normally distributed and the number of observation for this study is 1219.

Table 2: Summary Statistics of Variables

	GDPP C	BCPS	DCPS	CAB	LDR	BD	MEV	FD	INF	EXR	REQ	ROL	GEF	CC	PI
Mean	1.090	2.935	0.605	0.902	0.999	1.125	1.938	1.857	2.283	2.104	-0.534	-0.545	-0.507	-0.429	2.542
Median	0.947	2.578	0.666	1.045	1.248	2.225	2.974	3.101	3.354	1.160	-0.693	-0.677	-0.704	-0.657	0.920
Maximum	2.673	4.242	7.664	4.131	8.225	6.926	9.675	9.679	8.848	3.722	7.000	1.890	1.990	2.139	8.056
Minimum	-1.816	0.166	-6.693	-4.222	-7.090	-10.06	-3.955	-4.035	-5.033	-0.267	-2.645	-2.606	-2.445	-1.868	0.434
Std. Dev.	1.420	2.261	1.353	1.462	1.564	3.853	2.857	2.802	3.065	2.743	1.439	0.982	0.910	0.901	4.382
Skewness	17.15	0.636	-0.274	-0.560	6.622	-1.372	-0.211	-0.608	-0.640	1.665	2.333	0.788	1.073	1.156	3.324
Kurtosis	374.2	2.400	9.590	3.610	122.1	4.151	1.813	2.149	2.524	4.700	10.26	2.979	3.620	3.610	15.46
Jarque-Bera	6985.	100.5	1537.	22.60	7110	450.2	80.61	111.8	94.69	710.5	3785.	126.4	253.9	290.5	105.1
Probability	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Observations	1206	1219	844	333	1187	1219	1219	1219	1219	1219	1219	1219	1219	1219	1219

Source: Authors’ Computation using Eviews 10

4.2 Unit Root Tests

As it is the convention, in the contemporary panel studies, to avoid spuriousness in the regression estimates, we employed Livine, Lin and Chu (LLC) unit root test and Im, Pesaran and Shin (IPS) unit root tests (See table 3). However, LLC and IPS tests are preferred as their estimates are more reliable and consistent compare to the traditional Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillip-Peron (PP) test. In the words of DeJong et al (1992) and Harris and Sollis (2003) these tests (ADF and PP) are not reliable for panel studies because they leads to over-rejection of the null hypotheses when it is true and accept H0 when it is false. Thus we adopted LLC and IPS unit root tests because they can solve the problem of over-rejection of null hypothesis and can be applied on panel data.

The Panel unit root test is based on the assumption that the variables are integrated of order I(0) or I(1). Table 3 shows that some variables are I(0) while some are I(1), which provides justifications for the use of ARDL bound tests. Before constructing our models, all variables are tested for stationarity and the order of integration with intercept and trends, intercept and none are determined as shown in Table 3. All the variables of both LLC and IPS are statistically significant at 1% level of significance and are integrated of different levels of integration I(0) and I(1). The results of the panel unit root tests confirm that most of the variables are non-stationary at the level. The different order of integration of the variables makes ARDL the preferred approach to this empirical study.

Table 3: LLC and IPS unit root test

Variable	LLC	Order of Integration			IPS	Order of Integration		
		Level	Difference			Level	Difference	
GDPPC	-9.484***	I(0)	-	Intercept and Trends	-8.516***	-	I(1)	Intercept and Trends
BCPS	-5.902***	I(0)		Intercept	-7.382***	I(0)	-	Intercept
DCPS	-24.94***	I(0)	-	Intercept	-3.448***	I(0)	-	Intercept and Trends
CAB	-3.550***	I(0)	-	Intercept	-6.189***	I(0)	-	Intercept
LDR	-7.342***	I(0)	-	Intercept	-7.833***	I(0)	-	Intercept and Trends
BD	-33.30***	-	I(1)	None	-22.58***	-	I(1)	intercept and Trends
MEV	-8.429***	-	I(1)	Intercept	-3.394***	I(0)	-	intercept and Trends
FD	-12.24***	I(0)	-	Intercept and Trends	-4.753***	I(0)	-	Intercept
INF	-6.866***	-	I(1)	Intercept	-21.42***	-	I(1)	Intercept and Trends
EXR	-8.661***	-	I(1)	Intercept	-4.755***	I(0)	-	Intercept
REQ	-14.13***	I(0)	-	None	-10.53***	I(0)	-	Intercept
ROL	-5.948***	I(0)	-	None	-19.71***	-	I(1)	Intercept
GEF	-28.53***	-	I(1)	None	-15.27***	-	I(1)	Intercept and Trends
CC	-14.07***	I(0)	-	Intercept	-14.18***	-	I(1)	Intercept and Trends
PI	-6.393***	-	I(1)	Intercept	-14.83***	-	I(1)	Intercept

Source: Authors’ Computation; ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% percent level of significance, respectively.

4.3 Stability Tests

The stability of the long-run coefficient was tested by the short-run dynamics using the cumulative sums of recursive residuals (CUSUM) tests to assess parameter stability (see Pesaran and Pesaran, 1997). Figures 4 below shows the plots for CUSUM test for models 1-4 respectively. The plots of the

CUSUM statistics falls inside the critical bands of the 5% confidence interval of parameter stability with $\Delta \ln GDPPC$ as the dependent variable which shows that there’s no evidence of significant structural instabilities in models 1-4. Therefore, the estimated results are stable over the studied period.

FIGURE 4: CUSUM STABILITY TEST FOR MODELS 1 – 4

Source: Authors Computation with the aid of Eviews 10

4.4 Pedroni and Kao Cointegration Test

Pedroni (1999) extended the procedure of residual-based panel cointegration tests, which he introduced in his write-up Pedroni, 1995). He recommends several residual-based null hypotheses of no cointegration in panel cointegration test statistics. Two within-dimension-based (panel- ρ and panel-t) and two between-dimension-based (group- ρ and group-t) panel cointegration statistics of Pedroni (1999). Panel- ρ statistic is an extension of the non-parametric Phillips-Perron ρ -statistic, and the parametric panel-t statistic is an extension of the ADF t-statistic. Between-dimension-based statistics are just the group mean approach extensions of the within-dimension-based ones. Group- ρ statistic is chosen because Gutierrez (2002) has found that this test statistic has the best power among the test statistics of Pedroni (1999), Larsson et al. (2001) and Kao (1999). Group-t statistic is considered because the data-generating process is appropriate for parametric ADF-type tests. And the within-dimension versions of these statistics are considered in order to be able to compare. However, when compared to the Fisher-type test (Johansen cointegration test), the Pedroni cointegration test has several tests for cointegration that allow for

heterogeneous intercepts and trend coefficients across cross-sections, unlike others. Again, in his paper, Kao (1999) describes two tests under the null hypothesis of no cointegration for panel data. One is a Dickey-Fuller type test, and the other is an Augmented Dickey-Fuller type test. Having found that all the variables are integrated of order I(0) and I(1), Pedroni’s within and between dimension results of the panel cointegration tests, together with Kao’s panel Cointegration test results on different sets of variables and models, are presented in table 4. Indeed, our intention in complementing Pedroni cointegration with Koa type of cointegration is for robustness check. Viewing from Table 4, Pedroni cointegration results suggests that there is the existence countegration between the variables since most of the P-values of the tests (panel-v, panel-rho, panel-PP, panel-ADF, group-rho, group-PP and group-ADF) are less than 5% critical level. This implies that we reject the null (no cointegration) and conclude that there is a long-run economic relationship between the variables of the models. And also the results of the Kao cointegration suggests that the null hypothesis of no cointegration be rejected since the p-values of ADF-statistic are less than 0.05 (5%) significant level.

Table 4: Pedroni and Kao Cointegration Results for Models 1-4

Models		Pedroni Residual Cointegration Tests							Kao Cointegration Test
		Within-Dimension				Between-Dimension			
		Panel-v Statistic	Panel rho- Statistic	Panel pp- Statistic	Panel adf- Statistic	Group rho- Statistic	Group PP- Statistic	Group ADF- Statistic	ADF -Statistic
Model 1	T-STAT/ P-VALUE	-4.615 (0.000)	6.395 (0.000)	-20.36 (0.000)	-13.46 (0.000)	8.118 (1.000)	-28.40 (0.000)	-12.48 (0.000)	-14.66 (0.000)
Model2	T-STAT/ P-VALUE	-3.442 (0.000)	-0.138 (0.445)	-10.86 (0.000)	-16.13 (0.000)	1.958 (0.974)	-15.09 (0.000)	-4.813 (0.000)	-8.437 (0.000)
Model 3	T-STAT/ P-VALUE	1.404 (0.080)	-2.356 (0.009)	-16.46 (0.000)	-15.81 (0.000)	3.489 (0.999)	-7.157 (0.000)	-6.207 (0.000)	-9.935 (0.000)
Model 4	T-STAT/ P-VALUE	-1.2617 (0.896)	2.575 (0.995)	-14.78 (0.000)	-12.65 (0.000)	4.832 (0.000)	-12.13 (0.000)	-10.46 (0.000)	-2.740 (0.003)

Source: Authors’ calculation with Eviews 10. Note: (.) represents probability values

4.5 Correlations between the Variables used in the Study

Correlation analysis is a statistical method used to evaluate the strength of relationship between the variables in the model. From the outcome of the cross sectional dependence test, it was observed that there are some presence of serial correlation among the variables, hence, in order to further test for some unobserved autocorrelations in between the variable, we carried out the correlation tests for models 1-4 as shown below in table 5 below and our target is to check if there is any serial correlation in the variables of the models. There is a positive correlation between gross domestic product per capita, BCPS, CAB, BD, MEV, FD and INF in model 1, this shows that commercial bank significantly perform crucial roles in economic growth and development as it is in line with economic expectations (Yakubu and Affoi, 2014; Aurangzeb, 2012; Olokoyo, 2011; McKinnon, 1973; Shaw, 1973; and Schumpeter, 1911). In model 2, negative

relationship exists between GDPPC, BCPS, DCPS, BD, ROL, GEF, CC and PI. This findings especially the correlation between gross domestic product per capita and governance indicator shows that the government of G7 countries and Africa nations should align their economies with proper development policies that will lead to financial sector development. Indeed, if the quality and effectiveness of governance of a nation is poor, it affect other macroeconomic variables in the economy like BD and PI was greatly affected by the quality of governance. This is evidential in estimates from model 3, the interactive values of bank credit to private sector, regulatory quality and role of law are negatively correlated with gross domestic product per capita. In model 4, there is a positive correlation between gross domestic product per capita and the interactive value of DCPS, REQ, ROL, GEF, and CC.

Table 5: Correlation Matrix Results

	GDPPC	BCPS	DCPS	CAB	LDR	BD	MEV	FD	INF	EXR	PI
GDPPC	1										
BCPS	0.525	1									
DCPS	-0.031	-0.498	1								
CAB	0.620	0.623	-0.775	1							
LDR	-0.634	-0.415	-0.879	-0.750	1						
BD	0.531	0.947	-0.852	0.576	-0.561	1					
MEV	0.715	0.770	-0.030	0.895	-0.659	0.691	1				
FD	0.690	0.548	-0.028	0.106	-0.201	0.827	0.917	1			
INF	0.698	0.761	-0.482	0.067	-0.685	0.742	0.883	0.897	1		
EXR	-0.353	-0.613	0.714	-0.121	-0.475	-0.238	-0.438	-0.405	-0.355	1	
PI	-0.648	-0.722	-0.221	-0.593	-0.569	-0.162	-0.594	-0.074	-0.108	-0.133	1

Source: Authors’ Calculations

4.6 Panel Regression Results of Long-Run and Short-Run Coefficients

Commercial banks have contributed immensely to economic growth as footed in the literature (Yakubu and Affoi, 2014; Aurangzeb, 2012; Olokoyo, 2011; McKinnon, 1973; Shaw, 1973; and Schumpeter, 1911). Due to impeccable growth functions commercial banks plays (mobilization of savings, loaning of funds to investor, etc), it is seen as an agent of economic growth of a nation. However, in this study using panel ARDL approach we investigate the impact of commercial bank development on economic growth and below are the estimated results of the variables of models 1 through 4.

The diagnostic test was conducted for all the specified models 1 to 4 and it was discovered model are well specified, no presence of autocorrelation, the variables are homoscedastic and the error terms are normally distributed since the p-values of the normality test, serial correlation test, Ramsey reset test and white heteroscedasticity test (0.000, 0.135, 0.004 and 0.078) for model 1, (0.000, 0.138, 0.000 and 0.237) for model 2; (0.000, 0.898, 0.000 and 0.174) for model 3 and (0.000, 0.265, 0.000 and 0.0980) are in line with the assumptions of the classical linear model. From the results of the huasman test of model 1 through 4, it was concluded that fixed effects are independent of the explanatory variables since 0.0012, 0.0355, 0.0147 and 0.0101 are less than 0.05. In model 1, the coefficients of BCPS, DCPS, FD, BD, and MEV depicted a negative and significant impact on gross domestic product per capita at 1% significant level. While CAB, LDR INF and EXR have a positive and significant impact on GDPPC at 1% significant level. Their estimated coefficients implies that with a unit increase in the variables GDPPC would be reduced by magnitude of -0.800, -0.948, 0.059, 0.330, -0.478, -0.934, 0.934 and 0.184745 all things being equal. In model 2, the BCPS, DCPS, ROL, and GEF has negative and significant effects on GDPPC at 5% and 1% critical levels and the BD, REQ, CC and PI positively impact the GDP per

capita at 1% level of significant. Their estimated coefficients shows that all things being equal, a unit increase the variables would lead to about -0.576, -0.620, 0.826, -0.166, -0.429, 9.256, -1.687 and 0.366 decreases in gross domestic product. Similarly in model 3, the interactive values of BCPS with REQ, ROL, CC, GEF and MEV all depicted a negative and significant impact on gross domestic product at 1% critical level. Their estimated coefficients shows that if the variables are increased by a unit, it would amount to -0.378, -0.609, -0.030, -0.874 and -0.562 changes in GDPPC all things being equal. In model 4, the results of the long run relationship shows that the interactive values of DCPS, REQ and ROL have negative and significant impact on GDPPC at 5% significant level, while interaction between DCPS, CC, GEF and MEV depicted a positive and significant impact on GDPPC at 1% critical level. They have estimated coefficients which shows that a unit increase in the variables would lead to about -0.168, -0.205, 0.408, 0.306 and 0.015 effects on GDPPC all things being equal. However, the coefficients were interpreted as long-run elasticity estimates and the behaviours of the variables are in line with the apriori economic expectations, since long run relationship exist between the variables specified in model 1 through 4. And this is in consistent with the findings of (King and Levine (1993), Miller (1998), Friedrich Von Heyek (1929), FitzGerad (2016)) among others.

The coefficient of ECT (-1) shows speed of adjustment from short-run to long-run and for all the models, since they are statistically significant with negative signs. The coefficients -0.649665, -0.345568, -0.688673 and -0.419747 are negative and significant at 1% level of significance. The magnitude of the coefficient implies that 64%, 34%, 68% and 42% of the disequilibrium caused by previous year’s shocks converges back to the long run equilibrium in the current year. Bannered eta 1. (1998) noted that significant lagged error term with negative sign is a way to prove that the established long-run relationship is stable.

Table 6A: Panel Regression Results for Models 1-4

Regressors	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
	Dependent Variable: GDPPC			
BCPS	0.080 (0.000)	-0.676 (0.010)		
DCPS	0.948 (0.000)	-0.620 (0.000)		
CAB	0.159 (0.000)			
LDR	0.020 (0.000)			
FD	-0.017 (0.000)			
D(BD)	-0.047 (0.000)	0.058 (0.000)		
D(MEV)	-0.963			

	(0.000)			
D(INF)	0.504 (0.000)			
D(EXR)	0.184 (0.000)			
REQ		0.786 (0.000)		
ROL		-0.079 (0.000)		
CC		0.256 (0.000)		
D(GEF)		-1.687 (0.000)		
D(PI)		0.366 (0.009)		
BCPS*REQ			-0.378 (0.000)	
BCPS*ROL			-0.609 (0.000)	
BCPS*CC			0.092 (0.000)	
BCPS*D(GEF)			-0.874 (0.000)	
BCPS*D(MEV)			-0.562 (0.000)	
DCPS*REQ				-0.168 (0.003)
DCPS*ROL				-0.205 (0.016)
DCPS*CC				0.408 (0.000)
DCPS*D(GEF)				0.391 (0.000)
DCPS*D(MEV)				0.015 (0.001)
HAUMAN TEST	27.47 (0.001)	16.52 (0.035)	8.417 (0.014)	9.517 (0.011)
COINTEQ01	-0.649 (0.000)	-0.345 (0.000)	-0.688 (0.000)	-0.419 (0.000)
Constant	-3.565	---	6.410	---
Diagnostic Tests				
Normality	1371 (0.000)	135.0 (0.000)	905.8 (0.000)	503.0 (0.000)
Serial Correlation	2.004 (0.135)	3.262 (0.138)	0.107 (0.898)	1.328 (0.265)
Functional Form	-0.835 (0.004)	-0.258 (0.003)	-0.164 (0.000)	-0.736 (0.001)
Heteroscedasticity	2.020 (0.078)	1.630 (0.237)	2.660 (0.174)	2.530 (0.098)

Source: Authors' Calculations using Eviews10. Notes: The maximum number of lags for each variable is set at one, and optimal lag lengths are selected by the AIC. The ARDL estimators are computed by a 'back-substitution' logarithm, ****1% significance level, ** 5% level of significance and *10% level of significance.

4.7. Impact of Commercial Bank Development on Economic Growth in G7 Countries

In this section, we further disintegrated our data focusing on regions in order to ascertain the regional specific effects. Bearing in mind that a conventional step a researcher would take in specifying his model in any study is to diagnose the characteristics of the data, we subjected all the models to diagnostic test and from the estimated results obtained, it shows that the models (models 5-8) are normally distributed, has no evidence of serial correlation, possess correct functional form and their variance are homoscedastic (non-stochastic), since the p-values (0.000, 0.125, -0.004 and 0.738, for model 5); (0.000, 0.316, 0.000 and 0.188, for model 6); (0.000, 0.930, 0.000 and 0.385, for model 7); and (0.000, 0.630, 0.001 and 0.113, for model 8) are statistically significant and satisfies the assumptions of classical linear model (see: Gujarati, D. (2004)). The hausman test was carried out on the models (5-8) to determine if the model would favour fixed effects or random effects and our conclusion is that fixed effects are independent of the explanatory variables since the p-values (0.000, 0.005, 0.012 and 0.008) are less than 0.05; therefore, the models were estimated using fixed effect. In model 5, the results for the long run relationship shows that the BCPS, FD, MEV, INF and EXR have negative and significant impact on gross domestic product per capita at 1% significant level. While DCPS, CAB, LDR and BD depicted a positive and significant impact on gross domestic product at 1% level of significance.

Their coefficients shows that all things being equal, their unit increase would amount to changes in GDPPC at -0.015, 0.619, 0.617, 0.013, -0.055, 0.139, -5.048 and -10.38 magnitude. In model 6, the BCPS, DCPS, BD, REQ, ROL and PI have negative and significant impact on GDPPC at 1% and 5% critical level. While CC and GEF have positive and significant impact on GDP per capita at 1% critical level. This shows that a unit increase in the variables would cause changes in GDPPC by a magnitude of -0.286, -0.627, -0.450, -2.598, -5.500, 18.17, 4.957 and -90.52 all things being equal. In model 7, the long run relationship of the variables shows that the interactive value of BCPS, REQ, ROL, BD and MEV impacted the GDP per capita negatively at 1% and 5% levels of significance. While the BCPS and its interactive values CC and GEF have a positive and significant impact in gross domestic product per capita at 1% critical level. This implies that if there is a unit increase in the variables, it would amount to -0.156, -0.440, 0.379, 0.540 and -0.106 changes in the GDPPC all other things being equal. In model 8, the results of the long run relationship depicts the DCPS and its interactive variables ROL, GEF and MEV negatively impact the GDPPC at 1% level of significance. While its interactive variables REQ and CC depicted negative and significant impact on GDPPC at 1% level of significance. And this shows that a unit increase in the variables would lead to about 0.288, -2.305, 4.019, -13.23 and -1.506 changes in GDPPC all things being equal.

Table 6B: Panel Rgression Results for G7

Regressors	Model 5	Model 6	Model 7	Model 8
	Dependent Variable: GDPPC			
BCPS	0.015 (0.009)	-0.286 (0.000)		
DCPS	0.619 (0.001)	-0.627 (0.000)		
CAB	0.617 (0.000)			
LDR	0.013 (0.003)			
FD	-0.055 (0.000)			
D(BD)	0.139 (0.000)	-0.490 (0.017)		
D(MEV)	-0.669 (0.000)			
D(INF)	-0.548 (0.000)			
D(EXR)	-0.081 (0.000)			
REQ		-0.494 (0.000)		
ROL		-0.346		

		(0.000)		
CC		0.817 (0.006)		
D(GEF)		0.957 (0.000)		
D(PI)		-0.552 (0.001)		
BCPS*REQ			-0.115 (0.000)	
BCPS*ROL			-0.440 (0.000)	
BCPS*CC			0.379 (0.000)	
BCPS*D(GEF)			0.540 (0.000)	
BCPS*D(MEV)			-0.106 (0.000)	
DCPS*REQ				0.288 (0.009)
DCPS*ROL				-0.305 (0.000)
DCPS*CC				0.019 (0.000)
DCPS*D(GEF)				-0.623 (0.000)
DCPS*D(MEV)				-0.506 (0.000)
Hauman Test	13.05 (0.000)	14.257 (0.005)	9.931 (0.013)	16.52 (0.000)
Cointeq01	-0.938 (0.004)	-0.422 (0.003)	-0.583 (0.000)	-0.548 (0.001)
CONSTANT	---	---	---	---
Diagnostic Tests				
Normality	3257. (0.000)	2505. (0.000)	2904. (0.000)	3075. (0.000)
Serial Correlation	0.125 (0.882)	1.160 (0.316)	0.072 (0.930)	0.463 (0.630)
Functional Form	-0.129 (0.004)	-0.081 (0.000)	0.186 (0.000)	0.232 (0.001)
Heteroscedasticity	0.722 (0.738)	1.393 (0.188)	1.075 (0.380)	2.228 (0.113)

Source: Authors' Calculations using Eviews10. Notes: The maximum number of lags for each variable is set at one, and optimal lag lengths are selected by the AIC. The ARDL estimators are computed by a 'back-substitution' logarithm, ****1% significance level, ** 5% level of significance and *10% level of significance.

4.8 Impact of Commercial Bank Development on Economic Growth in Africa

The variables of the model was subjected to diagnostic tests to avoid spurious regression Gujarati D (2004). For all the models, the results indicates that the models are normally distributed, serially uncorrelated, well specified, and homoscedastic since there p-values are statistically significance (see table 6c). Fixed effect model is the

appropriate estimation process for the models since the p-values 0.0354, 0.0399, 0.0000 and 0.0037 are less than 0.05. Therefore, we estimated our models (9, 10, 11 and 12) using the fixed effects. Again observing from table 6c, in model 9, the results of the estimated coefficients of the long run relationship shows that BCPS, DCPS, LDR, and EXR depicted a positive and significant impact on GDPPC at 1% level of significant; while CAB, FD, BD, MEV and INF negatively influence GDP per capita at 1% level of significance. Their coefficients suggest that a unit increase in

the variables would cause changes in GDPPC by the magnitude of -0.007654, -0.000593, 0.336532, -0.002759, 0.018163, 0.068021, 0.086874, 3.063973 and -0.328464 all things being equal. In model 10, the results suggests that BCPS BD, REQ and CC have negative impacts on GDPPC at 1% and 5% levels of significance, while DCPS, ROL, GEF and PI depicted positive influence on GDPPC at 1% and 5% significant levels. It further suggests that increasing the values of the variables by any single unit would amount to about -0.028266, 0.044919, -0.007797, -0.915998, 1,269172, -3.523205, 1.252044 and 0.320333 changes in the GDPPC all things being equal. The results from model 11 shows that the BCPS and its interactive variables GEF and MEV depicted a

negative influence on GDPPC at 1% critical levels and with REQ, ROL and CC it has negative influence on GDPPC at 1% critical level. The result also shows that a unit increase in the variables would cause changes in GDPPC by a magnitude of 0.002, 0.007, 0.011, -0.009 and -0.002 all things being equal. Finally in model 12, the coefficients of the long run relationship shows that DCPS and its interactive values REQ, CC and MEV have negative impacts on GDPPC at 1% level of significance, and with ROL and GEF shows a positive influence on GDPPC at 1% level of significance. The result suggest that a single increase in the variables would cause a significant change in GDPPC by a magnitude of -0.064, 0.221, -0.420, 0.438 and -0.001, all things being equal.

Table 6C: Panel Results for Africa

Regressors	Model 9	Model 10	Model 11	Model 12
	Dependent Variable: GDPPC			
BCPS	0.654 (0.000)	-0.268 (0.000)		
DCPS	0.593 (0.000)	0.044 (0.006)		
CAB	0.336 (0.000)			
LDR	-0.759 (0.007)			
FD	0.018 (0.000)			
D(BD)	0.068 (0.012)	-0.797 (0.035)		
D(MEV)	0.086 (0.000)			
D(INF)	3.063 (0.000)			
D(EXR)	-0.328 (0.000)			
REQ		-0.915 (0.000)		
ROL		1.260 (0.017)		
CC		-3.523 (0.000)		
D(GEF)		1.252 (0.000)		
D(PI)		0.320 (0.005)		
BCPS*REQ			0.545 (0.002)	
BCPS*ROL			0.426 (0.002)	
BCPS*CC			0.281 (0.005)	
BCPS*D(GEF)			-0.069 (0.000)	

BCPS*D(MEV)			-0.535 (0.000)	
DCPS*REQ				-0.653 (0.000)
DCPS*ROL				0.221 (0.002)
DCPS*CC				-0.420 (0.000)
DCPS*D(GEF)				0.438 (0.000)
DCPS*D(MEV)				-0.011 (0.008)
Hauman Test	17.98 (0.035)	14.96 (0.039)	80.80 (0.000)	9.715 (0.003)
Cointeq01	-0.324 (0.000)	-0.611 (0.000)	-0.843 (0.000)	-0.732 (0.000)
Constant	---	2.907	---	2.7932
Diagnostic Tests				
Normality	162.0 (0.000)	102.0 (0.000)	993.2 (0.000)	127.0 (0.000)
Serial Correlation	1.388 (0.249)	0.281 (0.754)	0.626 (0.428)	0.231 (0.630)
Functional Form	-0.304 (0.000)	-0.012 (0.000)	-0.013 (0.000)	-0.013 (0.000)
Heteroscedasticity	0.067 (0.938)	0.199 (0.349)	1.323 (0.177)	1.070 (0.327)

Source: Authors' Calculations using Eviews10. Notes: The maximum number of lags for each variable is set at one, and optimal lag lengths are selected by the AIC. The ARDL estimators are computed by a 'back-substitution' logarithm, ****1% significance level, ** 5% level of significance and *10% level of significance.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The paper examines the impact of commercial bank development on economic growth using annual data series spanning from 1996 to 2018. We employed Panel ARDL bound testing methodology for the investigation. With data from G7 and Africa spanning from 1996 to 2018. The study takes into account the commercial bank development variables, macroeconomic and government indicator's variables to properly account for the ability of the banks and other financial institutions to receive money from the economic agents and the willingness of the individual economic agents are to deposit their money in the bank. The results of Pedroni cointegration test indicate that Gross Domestic Product Per Capita, Bank Credit To The Private Sector, Domestic Credit To The Private Sector, Current Account Balance, Lending Rate, Bank Deposits, Macroeconomic Volatility, Financial Deepening, Inflation Rate, Exchange Rate, Regulatory Quality, Rule Of Law, Government Effectiveness, Control Of Corruption and Personal Income shared a long run relationship over the studied period. In most of the models bank credit to the private sector have negative influence on economic growth,

this could be due to none performing the business climate, marked by socioeconomic problems and weaknesses of the judicial system, which prevents the enforcement of guarantees, thus contributing to private sector defaults. We therefore conclude that commercial bank development no doubt contributes significantly to economic growth.

5.2 Policy Recommendation

In order to achieve sustainable economic growth, the development of the commercial banks should not be overlooked in any economy since it has numerous role it plays in economic growth. Financial deepening, financial inclusion and technological integration leads to faster development of commercial banks. Therefore, policymakers should be focused on long-run policies to enhance the financial sector development. The policy-makers should also focus on formulating the policies that provides a favourable environment for private sector to grow. Again, government of the sampled economies should be more steadfast in her governance and quality of regulations in their economies since economies with stable governance attract investors, unlike her counterparts. Viewed in this way, commercial banks of G7 and African nations will be developed and success will be recorded in their level of economic growth.

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